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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION TRENDS IN THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION

II International Scientific and Theoretical Conference

17 DECEMBER 2023

Université Grenoble Alpes, FRANCE

CSIR-Central Mechanical Engineering Research Institute, INDIA

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STRATEGIES FOR TRANSLATING ENGLISH NEOLOGISMS INTO UZBEK, A CASE STUDY OF MEDIA TEXTS

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Abstract

This article delves into the translation strategies for transferring English neologisms into the Uzbek language within media materials. It explores the encountered challenges and proposes effective methods to address these issues, aiming to provide insights for translators and language professionals working with English and Uzbek in the media context.

Key words

translation, neologisms, English influence, Uzbek language, media context, linguistic challenges, communicative nuances

Introduction

In today's globalized world, the influence of English on other languages, including Uzbek, has become increasingly prominent, particularly within the realm of media and communication. The widespread use of English neologisms in media materials presents a significant challenge for translators working with the Uzbek language. This article aims to delve into the translation strategies employed for transferring English neologisms into Uzbek within media contexts, addressing the encountered challenges and proposing effective methods to overcome these issues.

Literature Review. Previous studies have highlighted the impact of English neologisms on various languages, yet there is a limited focus on Uzbek. Existing literature offers insights into translation challenges and strategies, but there is a lack of in-depth analysis within the specific context of media texts. This review aims to bridge this gap and build upon existing research to provide a comprehensive understanding of the translation dynamics between English and Uzbek in media materials.

The rapid evolution of technology and communication has led to the creation of numerous English neologisms, which are often integrated into media content such as news articles, social media posts, and advertising materials. These neologisms, originating from English, may not have direct equivalents in Uzbek, posing a considerable obstacle for translators seeking to convey the intended meaning and nuances of the original text. As a result, it is essential for language professionals and translators to develop effective strategies for handling English neologisms within the Uzbek media context [1, 129].

One of the primary challenges faced by translators working with English neologisms in Uzbek media materials is the preservation of communicative nuances. English neologisms often carry specific connotations and cultural references that may not readily translate into Uzbek. As such, translators must carefully consider the cultural and contextual implications of these neologisms to ensure that the intended message is accurately conveyed to the target audience [2, 97]. Additionally, linguistic challenges such as grammatical differences and syntactic structures between English and Uzbek further complicate the translation process, necessitating the development of specialized techniques to address these issues [3, 78].

To effectively tackle these challenges, translators and language professionals can employ various strategies for translating English neologisms into Uzbek within media materials. One approach involves adapting the neologism phonetically or morphologically to align with Uzbek linguistic patterns while retaining its original meaning and impact. Transliteration and borrowing from related languages are also viable strategies for integrating English neologisms into Uzbek texts, provided that they align with the linguistic norms and conventions of the target language. Furthermore, creating descriptive equivalents or utilizing existing Uzbek terms with similar semantic concepts can aid in conveying the intended meaning of English neologisms within media translations [4, 176].

The translation of English neologisms into Uzbek within media materials presents a multifaceted challenge that requires careful consideration and specialized techniques. By exploring the encountered challenges and proposing effective translation methods, this article seeks to provide valuable insights for translators and language professionals working with English and Uzbek in the media context. As the influence of English continues to permeate global communication channels, it is imperative for translators to adapt and develop innovative strategies to bridge linguistic and cultural gaps, ultimately facilitating accurate and impactful translations within the evolving media landscape [5, 189].

When working with English neologisms in media translation, it is vital for translators to consider the linguistic proficiency and cultural background of the target audience. Uzbek speakers may have varying levels of exposure to English and its neologisms, which can influence their comprehension and interpretation of translated media content [6, 87]. Therefore, translators must strike a balance between preserving the original impact of English neologisms and ensuring that the translated material is accessible and relatable to the Uzbek audience.

Furthermore, the adaptation of English neologisms in Uzbek media materials can contribute to the enrichment and evolution of the Uzbek language itself. Translators have the opportunity to introduce new terms, expressions, and linguistic innovations that align with the cultural and linguistic context of Uzbekistan. By carefully integrating English neologisms into Uzbek media content, translators can contribute to the expansion of the Uzbek language while maintaining its distinct identity and communicative effectiveness [7, 95].

In this context, it is crucial for translators to engage in continuous research and collaboration with language experts and native speakers to gauge the reception and understanding of translated English neologisms within the Uzbek media landscape. This collaborative approach allows translators to receive valuable feedback and insights from the target audience, enabling them to refine their translation strategies and ensure that the impact of English neologisms is effectively conveyed in Uzbek media materials.

Conclusion

The examination of translation strategies for English neologisms in Uzbek media texts has revealed the complex interplay between linguistic, cultural, and communicative elements. By identifying the challenges and proposing effective translation methods, this article contributes to the ongoing dialogue surrounding language adaptation and the impact of global media on Uzbek communication.

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